

Exploring Tipping Points and Their
Impacts Using Earth System Models

Milestone MS7

A report on the analogy between past and future vegetation tipping is provided to Task 8.1.1

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MILESTONE REPORT

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1. Means of verification

As stated in the Description of the Action, the means to verify that this milestone has been achieved is: “The document available on Zenodo in open access”.

2. About the work done to achieve this milestone

The TipESM project extensively investigates tipping in three terrestrial ecosystems: the Amazon rainforest, Sub-Saharan vegetation, and boreal forests in Europe. The objective of this milestone is to investigate analogies between past vegetation tipping points and possible vegetation tipping points in the future. There is thus a need to understand future tipping points as they emerge in climate projections, in particular in the core TIPMIP simulations, therefore in TipESM WP1, and past conditions. Most partners, such as the METO in Section 2.1.1 investigate the differences between pre-industrial and ramp-up/down experiments, whereas CNRS-IPSL considers simulations of the last 6,000 years. This milestone is based on preliminary results obtained with the UKESM1 and IPSLCM6 models, focusing primarily on Sahara-Sahel vegetation and boreal forests.

2.1 Sahel-Sahara region

2.1.1 Greening of the Sahel from a future climate perspective

In the future, the Sahara and Sahelian regions could experience more rainfall than today due to climate change. Wetter periods have occurred in the past and are associated with a moist vegetation landscape in contrast to today’s semiarid environment. The period of the Green Sahara in the Early Holocene and its rapid decline between 5 and 3.5 kyrs are illustrative of this (Pausata et al. 2020).

These past significant changes raise the question of what may happen under climate change, possibly leading to a tipping point to a ‘Green Sahelian’ region.

Figure 1 shows the simulated vegetation cover over the Sahel in the UKESM1.2 TipESM simulations. Vegetation cover generally increases with warming and is associated with an increase in precipitation. However, there is significant variability, particularly in the 4k zero-emission run, which is possibly indicative of threshold behaviour about a changing state.

Figure 1: Results from the UKESM1.2 simulations following the TipESM model protocol. 1) shows the extent of vegetation cover over the Sahel region, and b) the annual precipitation.

Understanding of past changes in the Sahelian region points to a role of a strong-land atmosphere coupling, where greening the Sahel can make rainfall more sustaining and therefore flip the state of the system. This has led to ideas about GeoEngineering; however, it remains highly uncertain, and the processes are not fully understood.

To further investigate, we have used UKESM1.1 AMIP simulations to test the climate impact of the African Great Green Wall. To represent the greening, we increase the Leaf Area Index (LAI) (by 1 m²/m²) in a band south of the Sahara, where precipitation is between 100 and 400 mm/yr. There is a strong latitudinal gradient in soil albedo, so that increases in LAI reduce albedo in the north and increase it in the south, and differences in exactly where the greening occurs will have different impacts on the surface energy budget. In our experiment, we generally observe an increase in absorbed shortwave, leading to small increases in latent heat flux and larger increases in sensible heat flux. There is little coherent impact on temperature or precipitation. The Great Green Wall targets a relatively narrow band of land, including some areas with low soil albedo, and more extensive greening of the Sahara further north would produce a more coherent surface energy budget response that could drive atmospheric feedbacks.

Figure 2: Difference between PFT and soil albedo.

Figure 3: Change in surface energy fluxes and near-surface air temperature due to increased LAI in the Great Green Wall region.

2.1.2 Analogy between Holocene and projected vegetation changes

The team at CNRS-IPSL is investigating whether analogies of tipping points found in simulations of the last 6000 years (mid-Holocene to pre-industrial) share some analogies with emerging tipping in future projections. For this, we performed a transient simulation from the mid-Holocene to 2100 with the IPSL model including dynamical vegetation. The model version corresponds to version 4 described in Braconnot et al. (2025). The simulation only accounts for natural vegetation, computed online. Land use was not included. Aerosols are prescribed to be those of 1850, as in the CMIP6 preindustrial simulation (Eyring et al. 2016). The external forcing is thus due to the slow changes of the Earth’s orbit and changes in trace gases.

The simulation has been extended to the historical period and to 2100, using the SSP4.5 scenario. All the simulations are concentration-driven. The emission-driven version of the IPSL model used in WP1 for the TIPMIP simulations is not yet compatible with the dynamical vegetation.

A key feature of the last 6,000 years is the rapid desertification that happened during the Holocene. We characterise aridification by considering the evolution of the desert area, defined as the grid cells in which the bare-soil fraction exceeds that of all other grouped Plant Functional Types (PFTs) (tropical trees, temperate trees, boreal trees, and grasslands).

Figure 4 shows that the simulated aridification is gradual, as expected from the evolution of the insolation, but punctuated by abrupt events. By analysing the spatial pattern (Fig. 5), we observe that the desert first extends southward in the eastern part, before the western part is affected, as already observed in the literature (Watrin et al. 2009, Lézine et al. 2011a, Dallmeyer et al. 2020, Hopcroft & Valdes 2021). The expansion is associated with a reduction of both the number of PFTs per cell and of the LAI. The 150-year projection from pre-industrial shows a reduction in the bare-soil fraction in the south-east, while the number of PFTs per cell and LAI increase. It indicates that the greening of the Sahara is a response to increased atmospheric CO₂. Also, the greening is fast compared to the time scales identified over the last 6,000 years. Interestingly, the greening of the Sahel/Sahara in the projection follows the reverse pattern compared to the Holocene desertification.

A preliminary result of this study is that the vegetation in the Eastern part of the Sahel would provide better constraints on the possibility of tipping points than the rest of the region. A preliminary evaluation of the vegetation between East and West seems to be in rather good agreement with what has been inferred from pollen and lake reconstructions (Lezine et al. 2011b), even though these reconstructions do not have temporal resolutions allowing for the detection of a tipping point.

Figure 4: Evolution of the desert extent in North Africa, as estimated from the bare soil fraction evolution, in a transient simulation with the IPSL model. The slow tendency is computed using wavelets.

Figure 5: Bare soil fraction over north Africa (row 1), number of PFT per cell (row 2) and LAI (row 3) in mid-Holocene (-6 ka, column 1), in pre-industrial (1850, column 2, plotted as the difference with column 1), and in projection (2100, column 3, plotted as the difference with column 2). On row 2, dotted areas correspond to desert areas following our criteria, and hatched areas to places where the bare soil fraction equals zero. All the quantities shown correspond to means over 31-year periods.

2.1.3 Analogy between AMOC-induced Sahel vegetation tipping point and future tipping point

We forced a tipping of the AMOC in a snapshot simulation with the IPSL model (Fig. 6) to evaluate its impact on vegetation systems in the Sahara/Sahel region (Fig. 7). As a response, the vegetation system becomes even more deserts in the eastern part compared to the effect of the insolation, confirming the higher vulnerability and more rapid changes of the vegetation in this region, in the IPSL simulation.

Figure 6: North Atlantic Deep Water formation [$S_v = 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$] of transient simulations with (grey) and without (blue) dynamical vegetation, and of a snapshot simulation (green) with dynamical vegetation and forced AMOC tipping. The green simulation is used to investigate the effect of AMOC tipping on vegetation dynamics, and is initialised by combining atmospheric and oceanic conditions from the blue curve to the vegetation maps of the grey one.

Figure 7: Bare soil fraction over north Africa (row 1), number of PFT per cell (row 2) and LAI (row 3) before (column 1) and after (column 2, plotted as the difference with column 1) a tipping of the AMOC. On row 2, dotted areas correspond to desert areas following our criteria, and hatched areas to places where the bare soil fraction equals zero. All the quantities shown correspond to means over 31-year periods.

2.2 Boreal forests

Using the Holocene transient simulation described in section 2.2, we also focused on boreal forests in northern Europe. The extent of the boreal forest is defined as the grid cells where the cover fraction of

boreal trees exceeds that of all other grouped PFTs (tropical trees, temperate trees, grasslands, and bare soil).

The extent of boreal forests (Fig. 8) does not undergo major changes along the Holocene, but exhibits variability at its limits. However, the 150-year projection from the transient simulation shows a clear expansion of boreal trees to the north, associated with a retreat at the southern limit. The expansion is associated with a change in the vegetation mosaic, as the 13 PFTs remain present, but those corresponding to boreal trees become dominant. In the southern part, the retreat is associated with the complete disappearance of boreal trees. In both cases, changes in boreal forest extent are associated with increases in LAI.

The projection of boreal forest behaviour as observed in our simulation has no analogy during the Holocene.

The tipping of the AMOC leads to vegetation changes in northern Europe in the opposite direction as changes induced by CO₂ forcing (Fig. 9). Analogies can be drawn with projections, especially for the northern limit that shows a clear retreat after the AMOC tipping. In the southern limit, mosaic changes favour boreal trees.

Figure 8: Boreal trees fraction over northern Europe (row 1), number of PFT per cell (row 2) and LAI (row 3) in mid-Holocene (-6 ka, column 1), in pre-industrial (1850, column 2, plotted as the difference with column 1), and in projection (2100, column 3, plotted as the difference with column 2). On row 2, dotted areas correspond to boreal forest extent following our criteria, and hatched areas to places where the boreal-trees fraction equals zero. All the quantities shown correspond to means over 31-year periods.

Figure 9: Bare soil fraction over northern Europe (row 1), number of PFT per cell (row 2) and LAI (row 3) before (column 1) and after (column 2, plotted as the difference with column 1) a tipping of the AMOC. On row 2, dotted areas correspond to boreal forest extent following our criteria, and hatched areas to places where the boreal-trees fraction equals zero. All the quantities shown correspond to means over 31-year periods.

3. Contribution to the TipESM objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following project objective:

SO6	<p>To identify tipping events in ecological and societal systems, with a focus on the climate drivers of these events, emphasising biodiversity, human health and habitability. KPIs: A report detailing ecological and societal TPs and climate thresholds that may cause tipping.</p> <p>Ref: Deliverables: D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3. Milestones: MS6 and MS7.</p> <p>The milestone MS6 report on the climate conditions that trigger tipping in ecological and social systems has paved the way for drafting the current milestone MS7. Milestone MS7 will support the preparation of the deliverable D6.2, the report on tipping in terrestrial ecosystems, which is due later in Autumn 2026. The present milestone investigates potential analogies that could inform the determination of emerging constraints in the frame of Task 8.1. A preliminary conclusion emerging from the analyses presented here is that a scope should be put on the understanding of vegetation feedbacks to define emergent constraints on vegetation tipping points. In particular, a focus should be placed on the Sahelian region in East Africa, which appears to be a sensitive region for both rapid shifts when an aridity threshold is reached and for cascading effects on vegetation in response to an ocean thermohaline tipping point. For the boreal forest, only the case of a thermohaline event appears relevant to provide constraints on possible tipping points.</p>	WPs: 1,3, and 6
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